

Research in the area of hospitality, with a cut in the business segment of small and medium-sized hotel companies in the State of São Paulo and its adequacy to the market of the current hotel sector.

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São Paulo
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Monograph presented to the University Nine of July - UNINOVE, as a partial requirement to obtain the Post Graduate Degree Lato Sensu, in Business Strategy, under the guidance of Prof. Dr Antonio Carlos de Alcantara

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THANKS

I am grateful to Leila Sollberger Jeolas, retired postdoctoral fellow at the State University of Londrina, for her guidance, criticism and direction in my journey through the principles of the academy, and her analyzes, discussions and considerations are crucial here. It certainly helped me clarify several logical and punctual aspects for the development of this monograph.

To the friend Paulo de Tarso Rodrigues that helped me a lot in the intelligence in the business of the tables, researches and support to several other projects of this nature.

Thanks also to Professor Andre Luiz Ramos who initially helped me to clarify several points on the subject of my monograph, guidelines and guidelines as well as all the professors responsible for the MBA - Business Strategy course in their guidelines and patience.

And those who were seen dancing were judged insane by those who could not hear the music.

Frederich Nietzsche

ABSTRACT

This academic thesis is the result of the bibliographic review research to elaborate the final work of conclusion of the specialization course *MBA* on Business Strategy postgraduate degree. The objective was to map studies carried out in the area of hospitality, with a cut in the segment of small and medium-sized hotel companies in the State of São Paulo. Information and data on this sector were also raised, which allowed to delineate a panorama of its current situation. The result of the research and the systematization of the data found will make it possible to indicate and subsidize future researches necessary in this field, especially on the adequacy of the sector to the existing hotel market. Existing Means of Lodging were surveyed according to hotel segmentation and current segmentation practices in the State of São Paulo, according to data from the Tourism Regionalization Program of the Ministry of Tourism. They include 28 consolidated macro tourist regions that have adopted the following parameters: geographical proximity, attractions and specific local tourist characteristics. These have been the basis for the development of programs and projects by the Government of the State of São Paulo. The data obtained and the literature review allowed to evaluate the current situation of the positioning of these companies. The results indicate that the adequacy and improvement of strategic positioning should be practiced for the improvement of its *Market Share* and, consequently, for the increase of the sales in order to keep them competitive in the market and aiming, mainly, the confrontation of modalities of *Disruptive* marketing.

Key Words: Hospitality. Services. Accommodation Means. Hotel Rating. Hotel associations. Non governmental hotel association. Hotel typology.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

IBGE – Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística

ABIH – Associação Brasileira da Indústria de Hotéis

CNC - Confederação Nacional do Comércio de Bens, Serviços e Turismo

EMBRATUR - Instituto Brasileiro de Turismo

FOHB - Fórum das Operadoras Hoteleiras do Brasil

INMETRO – Instituto Nacional de Metrologia,

MTUR - Ministério do Turismo brasileiro

OMT - Organização Mundial de Turismo

ONU - Organização das nações Unidas

SBCLASS - Sistema Brasileiro de Classificação de Meios de hospedagem

SEBRAE - Serviço Brasileiro de Apoio às Micro e Pequenas Empresas

UH - Unidade Habitacional

WTTC - World Travel & Tourism Coun

SUMMARY

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INTRODUCTION

The theme of this research is focused on the hospitality sector with a cut in the segment of small and medium-sized hotel companies in the State of São Paulo and its adequacy to the market of the current hotel sector.

The objective of this study was to map studies in this area, through a bibliographical and documentary review research. Information and data on this sector were also raised, which allowed to delineate a panorama of its current situation. The result of the research and the systematization of the data found seek to subsidize future research needed in this field, especially on the adequacy of the sector to the existing hotel market.

The justification of the work is due to the dispersion of the data found on the subject and to the need to systematize them in order to obtain a broad view of the sector, to be able to contribute to future research and, above all, to move towards a comprehensive and unique classification proposal for the hospitality industry.

Although there have been several attempts made by the Brazilian Tourism Company (Embratur) in the segmentation for small, medium and large hotels, a consensus has not yet been reached on hotel segmentation as well as the adhesion of participating hotels. The hotel classification developed by Embratur has always emphasized the physical aspects of the hotels, with about 70% of the classification requirements being focused on these aspects and only 30% on the service aspects, which is reflected to date in management issues (CASTELLI, 2003). The classifications did not take into account aspects such as managerial structures, financial performance indicators, characteristics of the clients' choices and the architectural aspect.

Some work assumptions were raised and objectified for the development of the research. Firstly, the role of the poor adherence by the hoteliers to the various attempts made by Embratur for a classification of segmentation in the country. From the reading of the bibliography on the subject, it can be said that this lack of adherence is mainly due to Embratur's classification model that prioritizes the physical aspects of the lodging facilities, leaving in second plane the managerial and architectural aspects. Another aspect of poor adherence is a possible lack of information, deployment and communication so that the hoteliers adhered to the proposed classification. It remains to

examine whether the classification proposals were focused and directed to the advances and growth of the types of hotels in the market and whether the fact that the hotels' membership was optional hindered the consolidation of a classification applicable to all establishments. The deepening of research in this area will allow us to evaluate what was really lacking in these previously proposed classifications.

The bibliographical survey carried out for this research showed the difficulties in creating a typology and hotel segmentation for the various types of hotels nowadays in Brazil, as well as in the world, due to the lack of consensus among owners of small and medium hotels and the organs governmental and governmental agencies that establish the classifications. What has actually shown the literature review is that there is room for improvement and execution of a segmentation hotel in the market more comprehensive and that takes into consideration the aspects mentioned here previously.

If a single hotel segmentation model is still not used consensually by the current market, it is also not practiced by small and medium-sized lodging in the state of São Paulo and Brazil, due to the lack of knowledge and lack of information on the subject in this sector . It is known that more than 80% of the existing hotel assets are independent, of small and medium size, thus opening a very large front of research and application in this area.

From this study, it is evident the need for a unique classification and segmentation model aimed at the small and medium means of hosting and that has the adhesion of the majority of the owners of the sector. The proposal of Vallen and Vallen (apud Carvalho, 2015) that emphasize the size, number of Housing Units (UHs), the category, defined by the amount charged for the average daily rate, the type of hotel, and the plan or system offered (meals and breakfast included in the daily rate); the classification proposed by Smith Travel Research (STR); and the work of the Forum of Hotel Operators of Brazil (FOHB) and Jones Lang Lasalle (JLL). The latter two emphasize the Revolving Room Daily, the average daily rate, the departmental costs and the Gross Income (GOP). In this way, the difficulties encountered with Embratur models, which have always prioritized only the physical aspects of hotels, can be overcome.

This proposal is presented as a future alternative to obtain greater success of the owners, especially if it is carried out by a non-governmental entity that does not create the resistances that are common when the proposals are presented by the government without the diagnoses and the necessary discussion next to the sector.

THEORETICAL REFERENCE: Application in the hospitality area with a cut in the segment of small and medium-sized hotel companies in the State of São Paulo and their adaptation to the market of the current hotel sector.

The art of receiving travelers comes from the beginnings of civilization when travelers needed a hostel in their various displacements and the development of the various means of lodging types has been receiving updates in the form of lodging and the types of establishments also followed this evolution .

The hotel industry is one of the main channels of tourism, with around 40% of the capital being attracted to the hostel sector (MARQUES, 2003).

As tourism reached world proportions in the 1960s, governments began to exercise greater controls and involvement in the tourism trade by ensuring higher quality of services offered (CASTELLI, 2006).

There has been a very qualitative leap forward in the development of government standards, procedures and involvement from the 1960s to today. With this evolution comes the classification of the means of lodging in Brazil prepared by the Ministry of Tourism focused on the physical aspects of construction, equipment and installation of the hotel business.

About 70% were focused on these aspects and only 30% on service aspects, reflecting to date on management issues (CASTELLI, 2003). The classification of the means of lodging did not take into account the segmentation of the market from the point of view of the hotel business, the user and the tourist.

According to Castelli (2003), the classification of hotels by quantity of stars has emerged in Europe (DUARTE, 2005), if necessary to guide tourists in terms of comfort, services and degree of services chosen in advance.

Although the consensus is worldwide known, there are difficulties in implementing a single system of classification, typology or segmentation since there are several types of accommodation and hotels today in the world market. In addition, cultural, geographic and political conditions vary from country to country, according to Frédéric Pierret in a document published by the WORLD TOURISM ORGANIZATION on hotel classification system.

Another reference is the existing segmentation practice in the United States of America, a type of hotel market classification that has created a scale for hotel chains and is widely used and followed by independent networks and hotels.

The classification was proposed by SMITH TRAVEL RESEARCH (STR), a consulting firm founded in 1985 by Randal Smith, who is renowned in the US market for data and comparative studies. The STR scale is organized through only six items: Luxury / Upper Upscale / Upscale / Upper Midscale / Midscale / Economy, according to the

average daily rate, type of establishment, from an architectural point of view, services offered and gross profit - Earnings Before Interest (EBITDA), taxes, depreciation and amortization performed on the billing. This facilitates the choice of customers by type of accommodation, the management system practiced and the vision of investors and hotel operators.

Returning to the Brazilian reality, although the Embratur attempt was valid in introducing a first classification of the means of lodging, the same classification was canceled in 1998, through Normative Deliberation nº 387 (DUARTE, 2005) due to the lack of credibility of the same.

Shortly after this attempt a new classification of the lodging facilities was reestablished by the National Institute of Metrology, Normalization and Quality (Inmetro), a fiscalizing agent of the Brazilian System of Standards. According to Castelli (2003), the hotel classification matrix approved in 1998 has four items that specify the types of lodging: Hotel - H; Historic Hotel - HH; Leisure Hotel - HL; Pousada - P. These four types of establishments were classified into five categories: Superior Luxury - 5 stars; Luxury - 4 stars; Standard Superior - 3 stars; Standard Single - 2 stars; Simple - 1 star.

In 2002 the Brazilian Association of Hotel Industries (ABIH), in partnership with Embratur, presented a new classification through the regulations. BRAZIL Brazilian Tourism Company n. 429, dated April 23, 2002, based on the requirements of comfort, service and care offered through voluntary membership.

This matrix evaluated establishments in six categories: Super-luxury hotels (five-star SL); Luxury (five stars); Superior (four stars); Tourist (three stars); Economical (two stars); and Simple (a star). Again with little adherence of the participating hotels, since it did not portray the existing reality of the market and the hotel segments.

A third attempt was made through the regulations of the BRASIL ordinance. Brazilian Tourism Company of n. 100 of June 16, 2011, taking into account three items related to infrastructure, services and sustainability with the star system as follows: Hotel (1 to 5 stars): means of lodging with reception and food service; Resort (4 to 5 stars): hotel with infrastructure for leisure and entertainment; Hotel Farm (1 to 5 stars): hotel installed in a farm or other type of agricultural exploration and that offers the experience of the rural environment; Bed and Café (1 to 4 stars): means of lodging offered in residences, with the maximum of three housing units for tourist use, where the owner lives on the premises, with breakfast and cleaning services; Historic Hotel (3 to 5 stars): hotel installed in building with historical importance; Pousada (1 to 5 stars): development of a horizontal feature, composed of a maximum of 30 housing units and 90 beds, with reception, food and temporary accommodation services, which can be in a single building with up to three floors, or have chalets or bungalows ; Flat / Apart Hotel (3 to 5 stars): means of lodging in building, with services of reception, cleaning and storage, consisting

of housing units that have a bedroom, bathroom, living room and equipped kitchen, with administration and integrated marketing, reception service, cleaning and housekeeping.

According to the Ministry of Tourism, there are approximately 15 thousand lodging facilities in the country, but only 7 thousand are registered in the system. On the other hand, another count made by the IBGE recorded 2,132 lodging establishments in the sense of 2001, last raised and available (IBGE, 2001). Based on this survey conducted for the research, it can be estimated that today there are more than 80 thousand means of hosting in Brazil.

Another important data source for the development of CBT and the bibliographic review was the remapping, performed and updated by the BRASIL ordinance. Ministry of Tourism, n. 144, of 2015, of the Ministry of Tourism Program for Tourism Regions (Ministry of Tourism, 2015).

It has 303 tourist regions, including 3,345 municipalities in the country. Among the criteria for the new mapping are: to have tourism offer among the municipalities that make up the regions; possess similar and / or complementary characteristics that identify the municipalities by historical, cultural, economic or geographical identity; be bordered or distributed contiguous, near or adjacent.

The research presented here will focus on the state of São Paulo, which covers 28 tourist regions with 222 municipalities according to this Ministry of Tourism document. In previous research conducted for this research, in the sales channels Trivago and Trip Advisor, there are 6.521 hotel developments in the state of São Paulo without presenting a segmentation. However, there is no body responsible for consolidating this information.

For this reason, the research is justified, as it will result in the constitution of a database segmented by Tourist Regions, Types of Means of Lodging, Cities and other parameters, allowing the knowledge of the current situation of each locality and tourist region, which will serve to sizing efforts and offering services and products.

Another important source of data for the development of this work is the sales channels used today by the means of hosting the small and medium-sized means of hosting, when known and available, through online reservations made on the hotels website itself. / or through sales channels. Today more than 2,000 types of online agencies are available in the market, such as Open Travel Agencies (OTA), also known as sales channels.

For the discussion of the means of reservations and technology available for hotels already available bibliography can be found on this subject. Technological progress and the tourism industry go hand in hand (POON, 1993; SHELDON, 1997). Since the 1980s, the Information Communication Technology (ICT) guidelines have transformed tourism through Information, and the development achieved changed the

management of business, strategies and also the structure of the Global Distribution System (GDS), a system of global distribution of reserves in the 1980s.

With the development of the Internet, in the late 1990s, we could observe large changes in the operational and strategic practices of the tourism industry (BUHALIS, 2003 apud BUHALIS, LAW, 2008).

The literature on the subject expands in the late 1990s, especially with the formation of a group of researchers focused on E-tourism, information technology in tourism, as well as the creation of the International Federation of Information Technology for Travel and Tourism (IFITT), under the coordination of Professor Hannes Werthner, and the publication of the Journal of Information Technology and Tourism (JITT).

Customers are increasingly looking for tourist information and hotel reservations directly on hotels' websites, or through existing sales channels, which was preferably done by tourism agencies and operators (MORRISON; JING; O'LEARY; LIPPING, 2001). The search for information on the various sites available not only reduces travel uncertainties, but also increases the quality of the purchase (FODNESS; MURRAY, 1997).

Customer reaction to online requests can influence satisfaction and behavior regarding the reservation, and as a result, this behavior becomes a key factor for the success of small and medium hosting (MAIN, 2001; RECHLANER; Page 2 Today, with several distribution channels and direct sales, the independent hotelier will have a much better chance of success (O'CONNOR and FREW, 2002).

Intermediaries, on-line travel agencies, On-Line Travel Agencies (OTA), can also assist in the static and dynamic distribution, such as availability and price, since more than 2,000 online agencies are available.

The literature review also indicates another fundamental factor in the evolution of the tourism and hospitality sector was the increase of baccalaureate, postgraduate and technical courses focused on tourism, hotels and other related disciplines. In Brazil, Marlene Matias, in the book "Tourism: Formation and Professionalization (30 years of history)", certifies that there were, at the end of 2001, 400 higher courses in the areas of Tourism and Hospitality. However, this does not reflect the existence of segmentation in the market. Another important event presented at the Panrotas Forum, "Tourism Trends 2017", was Luiz Paulo Luppa, a member of Trend, one of the largest tourism operators in Brazil, who emphasized the following: "Hoteliers need to learn how to segment to sell."
"

For the small and medium means of lodging in the state of São Paulo, according to the literature review, there is still a lack of empirical and academic evidence on the benefit of the means of lodging in relation to the existing data, which would allow a better formulation of prices and adequacy of their pricing according to the segment and

products offered, be they through an architectural differentiation, size, geographic location or through their daily practices in the current market. This shows that the information available, through scientific articles or market practices, is still a benchmark only for large hotel chains.

Considering what has been observed so far in this bibliographic review, it is reinforced that the classification and segmentation of independent hotels elaborated by Embratur does not take into account the selling price factor (daily).

Varian (2003), Pindyck and Rubinfeldt (2000) cite the importance founded by the microeconomic theory of the use of prices as a quality factor. Lewis (1997) empirically confirmed this aspect by showing the importance of price as an attribute used by consumers as a sign of the quality of a good or a service offered by the hosting media.

Figure 1 below by Siteminder, Australian technology company presents graphically how a reservation arrives to the establishment of a hotel, whether network or independent and the various sales channels available in the market as well as its pricing strategy for several sales channels, noting that there is a need for hoteliers to understand the price parity practiced in the daily rates for the various sales channels used.

Many small and medium-sized hoteliers still do not practice the same sales price for online sales channels, making it difficult for them to increase their hotel reservations and, at the same time, the final loyalty of a tourist or customer to their hotel establishment.

When an establishment owner understands that the daily pricing theme is also segmented by the type of housing available, ie that your hotel should be segmented according to the price practiced, existing architecture and the types of hotels available today in Brazil and in the world, it can practice differentiated rates between sales channels (online travel agencies, Open Travel Agencies - OTA) and market segments (travel agencies, operators and the corporate market).

In this way, the small and medium hosting medium can better work on your internal sales mix resulting in better financial performance for your hotel and segment.

Table 1 . Process of hotel reservation system

The Basics of a Channel Manager: A Guide for Independent Hoteliers 7

Fonte: Siteminder, empresa australiana de tecnologia (www.siteminder.com)¹

The challenge and the learning, provided by this project, will be to systematize information, in an accessible way, through information and communication technology (ICT), on the available channels of the distribution media of reserves, low cost and accessibility; on the financial results of the operation in a graphical and easy-to-interpret way; and on the segmentation of the means of lodging to better direct and position the small and medium establishments. Therefore, a better fit of your product against the current competitors.

This bibliographical and documental review identified small and medium-sized hotels in the State of São Paulo and contains the fundamental premises to achieve its strategic positioning, through the segmentation reviewed in this work.

Siteminder, launched by two Australian partners in 2006, focuses on all hotel sizes and today has more than 23,000 establishments in its portfolio, with presence in 160 countries, more than 350 partners in the distribution channels and more 250 partners

¹ A Siteminder, lançada por dois parceiros Australianos em 2006, é voltada para todos os tamanhos de hotéis e conta, hoje, com mais de 23.000 estabelecimentos em seu portfolio, com presença em 160 países, mais de 350 parceiros nos canais de distribuição e mais de 250 parceiros no sistema (CRS, PMS e RMS), alcançando faturamento na ordem de USD 16 bilhões e mais de 43.5 milhões de reservas (www.siteminder.com).

in the system (CRS, PMS and RMS), achieving revenues in the order of USD 16 billion and more than 43.5 million reserves (www.siteminder.com).

METHODOLOGY

There are several methodologies used in the elaboration of academic research, for its development and for its completion, achieving satisfactory results and in keeping with the challenges and problems raised by the researchers. The best fit of one and / or other is the result of debates and sometimes controversies between the authors and there are also different classifications of research with different emphases and interpretations about them (MAUCH; BIRCH, 1998). But what is a consensus among the authors is that the methodology used is directly related to the research problem, to the existing research and to the researcher's experience.

To better define the research problem and to define the methodology, it is always necessary a bibliographical review so that the proposal does not deal with themes and problems already researched exhaustively and with results and academic conclusions elaborated. It is fundamental, therefore, that the researcher is up to date with the problem raised and with empirical experiences proven in relation to its subject, and thus, to facilitate the systematics, procedures and results found, as well as the actions to be proposed for future actions.

The methodology is the "how" to solve the problems posed by the researcher, it is the path and the instrumental ones (methods and techniques used to give these answers.) Several authors, such as Lakatos and Marconi (2001) and also Cervo and Bervian (1996) (1993, p.23), "It is an activity of successive approximation of reality that is never exhausted, that is to say, it is an activity that seeks to answer questions and solve problems for proposed questions through the use of scientific methods. making a particular combination of theory and data. "In Gil's words (1991, p.19) academic research is a" rational and systematic procedure that aims to provide answers to the problems that are proposed. "

The choice of methodology to be applied as well states (KOECH, 1997, p. 125), therefore, depends on the aims and purposes of the research. For the author, there is no methodology more or less valid in itself, because it is the way to be covered to better solve the problems posed. In this way it is "legitimate and appropriate to show the scientific and the type of research is the most appropriate to the nature of the problem analyzed."

The choice of the best methodology for the research proposed here on segmentation of small and medium-sized hotels in the state of São Paulo, as mentioned

above, should respond to the research objective that is to know the situation of these means of lodging and the types of segmentation or classification used in this market. In a previous bibliographic review, it can be verified that there is not yet enough academic bibliography to validate and / or assure which typologies of segmentation or classification exist in the market are used. For this reason, the work proposes to make a bibliographical review on the subject and a survey of existing data available on these means of hosting and which types of segmentation or classification are used.

In this case, the best methodology is the bibliographical and documentary research that includes sources such as tables, reports and official documents produced, since it covers the bibliography made public in relation to the topic of study, from academic publications, newsletters, magazines, internet, among other means, to oral communications: radio, recordings on magnetic tape and audiovisual: film and television. According to Lakatos and Marconi (1996, p.66) "Its purpose is to put the researcher in direct contact with everything that has been said, written or filmed on a certain subject".

To reinforce the topic of bibliographic research, Vergara (2000, p. 48) states that it provides instrumental for any research, but also says that it can be "exhausted in itself." The importance of bibliographic research in the development of research can not be denied, and Fachin (2001, p. 125) sums up its importance "[...] is the basis for other research and can be said to be a constant in life of whom he proposes to study".

Aware of the advantages and limitations of all methodologies, the bibliographic research will certainly make it possible to advance in a wider range of data and sources, presupposing to carry out a direct research later. The main disadvantage is dependence on secondary sources that may compromise the quality of the result and the work itself (GIL, 1991, p.50). For this reason, several sources will be used to avoid unreliable data and sources and to ensure the quality of the final work, since it can serve as a basis for future work.

For the purpose of this bibliographic research methodology the researcher assumes that a quantity of empirical experience and constant search of information to final work, since it can serve as a basis for future work.

For the purpose of this bibliographic research methodology the researcher assumes that a quantity of empirical experience and constant search of information the proposed theme has already been developed and should be improved in this work of CBT, but the bibliographic review and the most suitable for this stage of tcc.

DATA ANALYSIS

Hotel segmentation has been gaining prominence in the most diverse attempts made by Embratur and the Ministry of Tourism in the last decades to classify and segment the means of lodging in Brazil. They were imposed by a hotel classification system to enter the hotels in the physical context of the classification. The various classification attempts were based on the physical aspects of the lodging and pre-established standards in the number of housing units, types of services offered, such as room service, number of restaurants, swimming pools and other physical aspects of a hotel. They did not take into account the managerial aspects, the financial indicators and the architectural aspects, using only star system classification criteria and, thus, making it difficult for the client to choose.

Classification and hotel segmentation gained strength in the 1990s and 1980s in Brazil, through the classification of the star system - hotels from 1 to 5 stars - but practically no longer used by hotels at the time, due to the poor adherence of hoteliers and emergence of new typologies.

The most recent tourism regionalization program of the Ministry of Tourism comprises 28 consolidated macro tourist regions that have adopted the following classification parameters: geographical proximity, attractions and specific local tourist characteristics. These parameters have been the basis for the development of programs and projects by the Government of the State of São Paulo, classifying, however, only tourist destinations and not the segmentation of existing lodging facilities and proposing a new classification and segmentation of hotel assets. The same program pointed not only to the tourist macro regions, but also to the tourist regions.

The bibliographic research presented here focused on the state of São Paulo, which covers 28 tourist regions with 222 municipalities, according to table 1 below. The Tourism Map is divided according to the categorization of the municipalities of the tourist regions in A, B, C, D, E and identifies the performance of the tourism economy to make it easier to identify and support each of the establishments according to figure 2.

Figure 2. Macro and Tourist Regions of the State of São Paulo

Table 1. Categorization of the municipalities of the tourist regions of the state of São Paulo

CATEGORIA	2013	2016	DIFERENÇA
A	10	10	0
B	34	31	-3
C	112	65	-47
D	336	101	-235
E	153	15	-138
TOTAL	645	222	-423

Fonte: www.mapa.turismo.gov.br

In addition to this survey, the Trivago and Trip Advisor sales channels, which include 6,521 hotel developments in the state of São Paulo, were also the focus of this study, also classified by type and segment, as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. List of municipalities and number of hotels per municipality

Relação municípios e quantidade de hotéis							
	QTD-HOTÉIS	CAT					
REGIÕES TURÍSTICAS		A	B	C	D	E	TOTAL
⊕ ABCTUR			34	18			52
⊕ Águas Sertanejas / Vale do Rio Grande			203		3		206
⊕ Águas Vivas					3		3
⊕ Águas, Cultura e Negócios			38		2		40
⊕ Alta Mogiana	91			10	4	0	105
⊕ Alto Tietê Cantareira			67	20	18		105
⊕ Alto Vale do Ribeira				13	3		16
⊕ Bem Viver	110	236	123	18			487
⊕ Café com Leite				5	25		30
⊕ Café e Flores				14			14
⊕ Caminhos da Mata Atlântica				95	4	3	102
⊕ CAPITAL	1.363						1.363
⊕ Centro Paulista			17	0	5		22
⊕ Coração Paulista			38	24	16	0	78
⊕ Costa da Mata Atlântica	671	275	7				953
⊕ Entre Rios				5	1		6
⊕ Grande Oeste de São Paulo				28	3	0	31
⊕ Grandes Lagos				8	1	0	9
⊕ Itupararanga Sorocabana			99	42	4	3	148
⊕ Lagos do Rio Grande			10	2	3	0	15
⊕ Litoral Norte de São Paulo	969	540					1.509
⊕ Pólo Cuesta			20	15	19	0	54
⊕ Serra do Itaqueri			28	101	9	0	138
⊕ Sol do Oeste / Águas do Oeste / Pontal Paulista			25	21	3	0	49
⊕ Tiete Vivo / Natureza e Tradições			20	8	0		28
⊕ Vale do Paraíba e Serras	487	100	279	17	1		884
⊕ Vale do Paranapanema / Vertente das Águas Limpas / Alto Cafezal			22	14	30		66
⊕ Verde Sudoeste Paulista				3	5		8
TOTAL	3.691	1.772	855	196	7		6.521

Fonte: sites Trivago. www.trivago.com.br e *Trip Advisor*. www.tripadvisor.com.br

Another source of data for this study was the contact with the Brazilian Hotel Industry Association (ABIH) to investigate the availability of data on the number of hotels in the state of São Paulo, and in Brazil as a whole, and the type of classification and segmentation used according to its performance profile. It can be seen that ABIH does not currently have parameters of segmentation and classification of hotels in general. The association works empirically and unstructured in relation to this data segmentation of the hosting media.

Another study by the bibliographical research was a survey conducted by Jones Lang LaSalle (JLL), a management and consulting company in the hotel sector, which showed in its 2016 report that there are no official hotel numbers in Brazil, nor its existing structure. For reporting purposes, they use their own database, market information and specialized websites, as well as using data from existing hotel chains to differentiate them from hotels independently. Other data used by them are the average daily rate, occupancy rate, revenue per available apartment (Revpar), and the financial

indicator such as Gross Operating Profit (GOP), known as gross operating income or Earning Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization (EBITDA), which translated literally into Portuguese, means "earnings before interest, taxes, depreciation and amortization" (EBITDA) as the main indicators in its analyzes, as shown in Graph 1 below (MADER et al., 2016).

Chart 1. International hotels and independent hotels

Source: Mader, Ricardo. Hospitality in numbers.2016. Available in:

<http://www.jll.com.br/brazil/pt-br/relatorios/127/hotelaria-em-numeros-2016>.

Accessed on: 31 May.2016.

In relation to the segmentation of sampling and the survey conducted by JLL, the hotels are divided and segmented as follows: Luxury hotels according to facilities, services and average daily rate in the order of R \$ 440.00; Hotels of superior category with installation and services of average standard, ranging from 3 to 4 stars depending on each market and with daily average between \$ 260 to \$ 440.00; Economical hotels - offer lean facilities and services with average daily rates below R \$ 260.00. (MADER, 2016)

Another bibliographic source found was the Forum of Hotel Operators of Brazil (FOHB) (<http://fohb.com.br/sobre-nos/quem-somos/>), a non-profit associative entity that brings together some of the most important hotel chains with country. Founded in 2002, it now has 27 associated networks, both national and international. There are 643 hotels associated with FOHB networks that together total more than 116 thousand housing units (UHs). They are present in 152 municipalities in the 5 regions of Brazil, generating more than 182 thousand direct and indirect jobs. By 2021, the hotels of the networks associated to FOHB will be 960, which will total more than 168 thousand rooms

(<http://fohb.com.br/home/>).

FOHB information is fed through JLL's reports and does not have a specific segmentation of the hotels or the existing number and data of hotels in Brazil. The bibliographic research work also sought data through the Syndicate of Hotels, Restaurants, Bars and Similar in São Paulo (Sinhores) that also did not present any type of hotel segmentation, according to data obtained through the website http://www.sinhores-sp.com.br/technical_data.html. The data found are as follows:

Tourism

São Paulo receives 10 million visitors annually. Of these, 16.54% are foreigners and 83.46 are Brazilian.

Of the international tourists, 38% are from Europe, 30% from the United States and Canada, 21% from Mercosur, 7% from Latin America and 4% from Asia.

Of the total of Brazilian and foreign tourists that the city receives, 73.5% come to business, 13.7% to leisure and 12.8% for other reasons.

The average stay in the city is 2.3 days.

The daily expenses of tourists is R\$ 224.38.

Hospitality

The main national and international hotel chains are here.

São Paulo has 410 hotels and 46,000 apartments available.

The average occupancy rate for hotels and flats in São Paulo in the first half of 2007 was 68%.

The average daily rate for the same period was R \$ 155.00.

350 motels.

The periods of highest hotel occupancy are, respectively: October 57.36%, June 56.51%, August 56.27%, November 56.23%, July 54.61%, March 54.20%, May 53.39 %, September 52.14%, April 47.93%, December 47.44%, January 40.42% and February 38.21%.

Another bibliographical reference that is worth mentioning refers to the American company Smith Travel Research (STR), since the segmentation presented by it is also used by FOHB and JLL. The company presents in an orderly way the segmentation of hotel chains and independent hotels as follows: Luxury - Upper Upscale - Upscale - Upper Midscale - Midscale - (Average Scale) - Economy (Economic Scale). It uses data from the previous year, the average daily, the management structures, the

architectural aspects of each network and type, as well as the presented results. Currently, this segmentation, or as it is called Hotel Chain Scales, is the form of presentation of the hotel segments most used at the moment in the American market, the Caribbean, and globally, being widely used to measure performance and results of the most varied hotel segments in the world according to tables 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8. Table 3 below shows all these segmentations.

Table 3. STR Chain Scales (US and Caribbean Hotel Networks Scale)

STR Chain Scales – North America and Caribbean

Luxury				Economy
21c Museum Hotels	Hyatt Regency	Hotel Indigo	OHANA	Affordable Suites
AKA	Joie De Vivre	Hyatt House	Oxford Suites	of America
Andaz	Kimpton	Hyatt Place	Park Inn	America's Best Inn
Belmond	Le Meridien	Larkspur Landing	Phoenix Inn	America's Best Value Inn
Conrad	Magnolia Hotel	Legacy Vacation Club	Ramada Plaza	Budget Host
Dorchester Collection	Marriott	Melia	Red Lion Hotels	Budget Suites of America
Edition	Marriott Conference	Miyako Hotels	Silver Cloud	Budgetel
Fairmont	Center	Novotel	Sonesta ES Suites	Country Hearth Inn
Four Seasons	Millennium	NYLO Hotel	Tryp by Wyndham	Crestwood Suites
Grand Hyatt	Omni	Prince Hotel	TownePlace Suites	Crossland Suites
InterContinental	Outrigger	Radisson	Westmark	Days Inn
JW Marriott	Pan Pacific Hotel Group	Residence Inn	Wyndham Garden Hotel	Econo Lodge
Langham	Pestana	Room Mate	Xanterra	Extended Stay America
Loews	Pullman	Shell Vacations Club		E-Z 8
Luxury Collection	Radisson Blu	Sonesta Hotel	Midscale	Family Inns of America
Mandarin Oriental	Renaissance	Springhill Suites	3 Palms Hotels & Resorts	Good Nite Inn
Montage	Sheraton	Staybridge Suites	A Victory Hotels	GuestHouse Inn
Palace Resorts	Starhotels	Stoney Creek	AmericInn	Home-Towne Suites
Park Hyatt	Swissotel	Vacation Condos by	Baymont Inn & Suites	Howard Johnson
Ritz-Carlton	Tribute Portfolio	Outrigger	Best Western	InTown Suites
RockResorts	Warwick Hotels		Candlewood Suites	Jameson Inn
Rosewood	Westin	Upper Midscale	ClubHouse	Key West Inn
Sixty Hotels	Wyndham	Ayres	Crossings by GrandStay	Knights Inn
Sofitel		Aqua Hotels	Crystal Inn	Lite Hotels
St Regis	Upscale	Best Western Plus	FairBridge Inn	Masters Inn
Taj	AC Hotels by Marriott	Boarders Inn & Suites	GrandStay	Microtel Inn &
The Peninsula	aloft Hotel	Centerstone Hotels	Residential Suites	Suites by Wyndham
Thompson Hotels	Ascend Collection	Chase Suites	Hawthorn Suites	Motel 6
Trump Hotel Collection	Aston Hotel	Clarion	by Wyndham	National 9
Valencia Group	Best Western Premier	Cobblestone	InnSuites Hotel	Passport Inn
Viceroy	Cambria Suites	Comfort Inn	Lakeview	Pear Tree Inn
W Hotel	Canad Inn	Comfort Suites	Distinctive Hotels	Red Carpet Inn
Waldorf Astoria	CitizenM Hotels	Country Inn & Suites	La Quinta Inn & Suites	Red Roof Inn
	Club Med	Doubletree Club	MainStay Suites	Rodeway Inn
Upper Upscale	Coast Hotels & Resorts	Drury Inn	Oak Tree Inn	Savannah Suites
Ace Hotel	USA	Drury Inn & Suites	Quality Inn	Scottish Inn
Affinia	Courtyard	Drury Plaza Hotel	Ramada	Select Inn
Autograph Collection	Crowne Plaza	Drury Suites	Red Lion Inn & Suites	Studio 6
Club Quarters	Disney Hotels	Fairfield Inn	Settle Inn	Suburban Extended Stay
Curio Collection	Double Tree	Golden Tulip	Shilo Inn	Sun Suites Hotels
Delta	element	Hampton Inn	Sleep Inn	Super 8
Dolce	EVEN Hotels	Hampton Inn & Suites	Vagabond Inn	Travelodge
Embassy Suites	Four Points	Holiday Inn	Vista	Value Place
Gaylord	Graduate Hotels	Holiday Inn Express	Wingate by Wyndham	WoodSpring Suites
Hard Rock	Grand America	Home2 Suites by Hilton	Yotel	
Hilton	Great Wolf Lodge	Isle of Capri		
Hyatt	Hilton Garden Inn	Lexington		
Hyatt Centric	Homewood Suites	MOXY		

Fonte: <http://www.hotelnewsnow.com/Media/Default/Images/chainscales.pdf>
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Table 4. STR Chain Scales (Scale of Hotel Networks in the World)

STR Chain Scales – Global

Luxury

Adrian Hoteles	Icelandair Hotel	Six Senses	Bella Vista Motel	H-TOP Hotels
African Pride	InterContinental	Sixty Hotels	Berkshire Rooms Serviced	Hand Picked
AKA	Isotel	Sofitel Luxury Hotels	Accommodations	Hard Rock
Aldemar	Jaz	St Regis	Blue Horizon Group	Hilton
Amanresorts International	Jumeirah	Taj Group	Boscolo Hotels	Hilton Grand Vacations
Anantara	JW Marriott	The Address Hotels &	Bridgestreet	Hoteles Othon
Andaz	Kamuela Villas	Resorts	Accommodations	Hotel Akena
Angsana Hotels & Resorts	Kempinski Hotels	The Leela Palace &	Bristol Hotels	Hotel du Vin
Armani Hotels & Resorts	Kenzi Hotel	Resorts	Caesar Park Hotels	Hotel Keihan
Baglioni Hotels	Langham	The Peninsula Hotel	Camino Real	Hotel Nikko
Banyan Tree	Loews	The Prince	Canopy by Hilton	Hotel Santika
Belmond	Lotte Hotels & Resorts	Thompson Hotel	Carlton Hotel Collection	Hyatt
Bulgari Hotels	Lotus Resorts	Tonino Lamborghini Hotels	Casa Andina Private	Hyatt Centric
Capella	Lungarno Hotels	& Resorts	Collection	Hyatt Regency
Cheval Residence Group	Luxury Collection	Trump Hotel Collection	City Marque	IC Hotels
Clarks Group Hotel	Mandarin Oriental	U Hotels & Resorts	Club Quarters	Instinct Hotel
Club Magic Life	Hotel Group	Valencia Group	Comwell	JA
Concorde Hotels	Mayfair Hotels & Resorts	Viceroy	Corinthia	Joie De Vivre
Conrad	ME	W Hotel	Cotels Serviced Apart-	Kimpton
Constance Hotels	Mint Hotels & Apartments	Waldorf Astoria	ments	Le Meridien
Cordis Hotels & Resorts	Mokara	Wanda Reign	Curio Collection	Legacy Hotels
Crown Hotel	Montage Hotels	Yadis Hotels	D Collection	Leonardo Boutique Hotel
Daiwa Royal Hotels	Niccolo	Zoetry Wellness & Spa	Dai-ichi	Leonardo Royal Hotel
Dorchester Collection	Niquesa Hotel	Resorts	Dan Hotels	Live Aqua
Doyle Collection	& Residences	21c Museum Hotels	Delta Hotels	Louis Hotels
Dreams Resorts & Spas	NOW Resorts & Spas	Upper Upscale	Derby Hotels Collection	Luca Hotels & Resorts
Dusit Devarana	Oberoi Hotels	Ace Hotel Group	Diego De Almagro Hotels	LUX*
Edition	One & Only Resorts	Adina	Divani Hotels	Magnolia Hotel
Elegant Hotels Group	Ovolo Group Limited	Affinia	Dolce Hotels & Resorts	Malmaison
Fairmont	Palace Resorts	Alila Hotels & Resorts	Dreamhouse Serviced	Mamaison
Firmdale Hotels	Paradissus Resorts	Apitour World Hotels &	Apartment	Marlin Apartments
Four Seasons	Park Hyatt	Resorts	Dusit Thani Hotels &	Marriott
Franklyn Hotels & Resorts	Prestige Hotel & Resort	Amarante Hotels &	Resorts	Marriott Conference
Fullon Hotels	Quay	Resorts	Electra Palace Hotel	Center
Gran Melia	Raffles	Amrath Hotels	Embassy Suites	Marriott Executive
Grand Hyatt	Regalia Hotel	Arjaan Hotel Apts by	Fireside Inn & Suites	Apartments
Guoman	Regent Hotels	Rotana	Fountain Court Apartment	Martí
Hipotels	Ritz-Carlton	Ascott	Frasers Hospitality	Martin 's Hotels
Hospes Hotels	RockResorts	Atlantic Hotels	Gaylord Entertainment	Melia Boutique
Hyatt Zilara	Rosewood	Autograph Collection	GHL	Meriton Serviced
Hyatt Ziva	Secrets Resorts & Spas	AVANI	Grand Prince Hotel	Apartments
Iberostar Grand Collection	Shangri-La Hotel		Granvia	Meritus Hotels & Resorts

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Fonte: <http://www.hotelnewsnow.com/Media/Default/Images/chainscales.pdf>

Table 5. STR Chain Scales (Scale of Hotel Networks in the World). Continued Upper Upscale Scale

STR Chain Scales – Global

Upper Upscale continued			
MGallery Hotel Collection	Sunscape Resorts & Spas	Appart'City	CitizenM Hotels
Millennium Hotels	Swissotel	Aranzazu Hoteles	Ciutat Hotels
Mitsis	Tangla Hotels	ARCOTEL Hotels	Clarendon
Myhotel Hotels	The LaLit Group	Arora	Clarion Collection
New Otani Hotels	The Marmara	Art Series Hotels	Classical
New World	The Park Hotels	art'otel	Clayton Hotels
NH Collection	Tivoli Hotels & Resorts	Aryaduta Hotel	Club Med
NHOW	Tokyu Hotel	Ascend Collection	Coast Hotels & Resorts
Nuran Serviced	Tribute Portfolio	Aston Hotels	Canada
Residences	Trident Hotel	AtaHotels	Coast Hotels & Resorts
Oakwood Premier	Victoria Hotels & Resorts	Atton Hotel	USA
Okura Hotels	Vida Hotels & Resorts	Austria Trend Hotels & Resorts	Copthorne Hotels
Omni	VITS	Axel Hotels	Coral Hotels & Resorts
Oro Verde Hotels	Vivanta by Taj	Azalai Hotels	Courtyard
Outrigger Resorts	Waldorf Apartment Group	B-Aparthotels	Courtyard Hotel
Pan Pacific	Wanda Vista	B4 Hotels	Crowne Plaza
Peppers Hotels	Warwick Hotels	Barcelo Premium	Dazzler Hotels
Pestana	West London Apartments	Be Live Hotel	De Vere Venues
Pullman	Westin	Best Western Premier	Derag Hotel and Living
QT Hotels & Resorts	Worldhotel	Bilderberg	Disney Hotels
Quinta Real	Wyndham Hotels	Blue Tree Hotels	Dwan
Quorvus Collection	Zhejiang Narada	BlueSun Hotels & Resorts	Dorint Hotels & Resorts
Radisson Blu		Bourbon Hotels & Resorts	Dormero Hotel
Rayhaan Hotels & Resorts	Upscale	Break Sokos Hotel	DoubleTree
Red Carnation	abba	Cambria hotel & suites	dusitD2
Renaissance	Abode	Canad Inns	Duxton International
Rixos	ABOU NAWAS	Centara Boutique Collection	Eastin
Rotana	AC Hotels by Marriott	Centara Grand Hotels & Resorts	Eaton
Sandton Hotels	acora Hotel and Wohnen	Centara Hotels & Resorts	element
Serena Hotels	AHA Hotels	Centara Residences & Suites	Elite Hotels
Shama	aloft Hotels	CenterHotel	ESA Serviced Apartments
Shaza Hotels	Alp Azur Hotels	Centra Hotels & Resorts	Esplendor Hotels
Sheraton Hotel	Alt Hotels	Central Apartment Hotels	EuroAgentur Hotel
SKYCITY Entertainment	AMAKS Hotels & Resorts	Chaaya	Eurostars Hotel
SKYCITY Grand	Amari	Chandris Hotels & Resorts	EVEN Hotels
Southern Sun - Sun Hotels	Amathus Beach Hotel	Chic&basic	Evenia Hotels
Spires Serviced	Amerian Hoteles	Chinas Best Value Inn	Ewa Hotel Apartments
Apartments	Ameron Hotel Collection	Cinnamon	Excel Hotel Tokyu
St. Giles Hotels	ANA		Fiesta Americana
Starhotels	Apa Hotel		First
Steigenberger Hotels	Apex Hotels		Four Pillars Hotels
Sun International	Apollo Hotels & Resorts		Four Points by Sheraton
			Fujiya Hotels
			Furama Hotels
			Garden Palace Hotel
			GHL Comfort
			Go Native Apartments
			Graduate Hotels
			Grand America Hotels
			& Resort
			Grand Dorsett
			Grand Hotel
			Grand Mercure
			Grand Metropark
			Grand Skylight Hotel
			Grand Skylight
			International
			Crowne Plaza
			Grand Soluxe Hotel
			Grange Hotels
			Great Wolf Lodge
			GrecoTel
			Gresham Hotels
			H10 Hotels
			Hampshire
			Hampshire Classic
			Hankyu Hotel
			Harbour Plaza Hotels
			& Resorts
			HARRIS Hotels
			Hastings Hotels
			Hayley Conference
			Centres
			Heartland Hotels
			HELIO PARK
			Hellsten
			Helnan Hotels
			Hongda Hotels & Resorts
			Hesperia Hotels
			Hil Hotels
			Hilton Garden Inn
			Holiday Club Resorts
			Homewood Suites
			Hotel Equatorial
			Hotel Grand Central

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Table 6. STR Chain Scales (Scale of Hotel Networks in the World). Continued of the Upscale scale (Upper Scale)

STR Chain Scales – Global

Upscale continued			
Hotel Grand Continental	Maritim	Rendezvous Hotels	Thistle Hotels
Hotel Guldsmeden	Median Hotels	Residence Inn	Thon Hotels
Hotel Husa	Medina	Resta	TIME Hotels
Hotel Indigo	Melia	Rica Hotels	Traders Hotel
Hotel JAL City	Metropolitan	Rimonim Hotels & Resorts	Transamerica
Hotel Jen	Mitsui Garden Hotel	RIU Hotel	Travel Inn Hotel
Hotel Monterey	Miyako Hotels	Robinson Club GMBH	Tsokkos Hotel
Hotel Occidental	Moevenpick	Rochester Hotels	UNA Hotels & Resorts
Hotel Pearl City	Monte Carlo Inns	Room Mate Hotels	Vacation Condos by
Hoteles Estelar	Mutiara Hotels & Resorts	Ryad Mogador Hotel	Outrigger
House of Fisher Serviced Apartments	New Century Grand Hotel	Rydgdes Hotels & Resorts	Vertice Hotele
HUALUXE Hotels & Resorts	New Century Resort	SACO Service Apartments	Victor's Residenz Hotel
Hyatt House	New Hotel	Safir Hotels & Resorts	Vista Hotels
Hyatt Place	NH Hotels	Sandals	Voyages Hotels & Resorts
Iberostar Hotels & Resorts	Nova Hotels	Sandman Signature	Wanda Realm
Iberotel Hotels	Novotel Hotels	Sarova	WelcomHotel
Imperial Hotels & Resorts	Novotel Suites	Sawridge Inns	Wyndham Vacation Resort
Inside by Melia	NYLO Hotel	Scandic Hotel	25Hours Hotels
InterCity Hotel Group	O' Callaghan Hotels	Sedona Hotels	
Jaz in the City	Oaks Hotels & Resorts	Shell Vacations Club	Upper Midscale
Jim Jiang Hotel	Oakwood Residence	Shire Hotels	Abotel
Jinling	Oceania	Silken Hoteles	Accord Hotels
Jolly Hotels	Onomo Hotel	Solo Sokos Hotel	Adagio City Aparthotel
K+K Hotel	OREA Hotel	Soluxe Hotel	Al Diar
Kipriotis Hotels	Original Sokos Hotel	Sonestta Hotel	Alfa Hotels
Landidyll Hotel	Oxford Hotels & Inns	Springhill Suites	Altis Hotels Group
Lapland Hotels	Palladium Hotels	Stamford Hotels & Resorts	Amber Hotel
Larkspur Landing	Paradores	Star Inn Hotels	Aqua Hotels & Resorts
Legacy Vacation Club	Parc Hotels	Staybridge Suites	Arcadia Hotels
Leonardo Hotels	Park Plaza	StayCity Serviced Apartment	Arcona Hotels
LifeClass Hotels & Resorts	PARKROYAL	Stoney Creek	AS Hotels
Lindner Hotels, Inc	Pearl Continental Hotels	Sunstar Hotel	Ashok
Loisir Hotel	Petit Palace Hotels	SuperClubs	Atura
Luxemon	Plaza Inn Hotels	Swiss-Garden	Avari Hotels
Maccdonald Hotels	Premier Apartments UK	The Gateway	Ayre
Maistra	Pride Resorts	The Heritage Hotels Group	Ayres
Maldron Hotels	Prince Hotels	The Pride Hotel	AZIMUT
Manotel	Principal Hayley	The Sebel	Barcelo Hotels
Mantra	Qualys Hotel	The Three Corners	Bastion Hotels
Marco Polo	Quest Apartment Hotels	The Triton	Bayview Intl Hotels & Resorts
	Radisson		Be Smart Hotel
	Regal Hotels International		

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Fonte: <http://www.hotelnewsnow.com/Media/Default/Images/chainscales.pdf>

Table 7. STR Chain Scales (Scale of Hotel Networks in the World). Continued Upper Midscale Scale

STR Chain Scales – Global

Upper Midscale continued

Dusit Princess
 Elba Hotels
 Fairfield Inn
 FJB Hotels
 Fleming's Hotels & Restaurant
 Floris
 Fortune Resorts
 Fortune Select
 Fosshotel
 Frantour
 FX Hotels Group
 Garden Court
 Gloria
 Golden Tulip
 Gunnewig Hotels
 Hallmark Hotels
 Hampton Inn
 Hampton Inn & Suites
 Hatton Hotels
 HCC Hotels
 Heritage
 Holiday Inn
 Holiday Inn Express Hotel
 Holiday Inn Garden Court
 Holiday Inn Select
 Home2 Suites by Hilton
 Hotels Slaviero
 Hotel Alpha-One
 Hotel Des Gouverneurs
 Hotel Edda
 Hotel Grand Chancellor
 Hotels
 Hotel Mets
 Hotel MyStays
 Hotel Royal Orchid
 Hotel Trusty
 Hotetur
 Hunguest
 Idea Hotels
 IFA Hotels & Resorts
 Ilunion Hotels

InterCityHotel
 Isle of Capri
 Jurys Inns
 Kagum Hotel
 Kyriad Prestige
 Leeden Hotel
 Legacy Hotels UK
 Lemon Tree Premier
 Lexington
 Lords Inn Hotels & Resorts
 Lynch Hotels
 Max Hotels & Resorts
 Mercure Hotels
 Metro
 Metropark
 MOXY
 My Fortune
 nestor Hotel
 New Century Hotel
 Norlandia
 OHANA Hotels
 Oxford Suites
 OZO
 Park Inn
 Park Regis
 Penta
 Phoenix Inn
 Princess
 Prodomo
 Protea Hotel
 Punhill
 Quality
 Quality Hotel & Resort
 Qubus Hotels
 Quest Hotels
 Ramada Plaza
 Rantasipi
 Real Inn
 Red Lion Hotel
 Regenta
 Reikartz Hotels & Resorts

relaxa Hotels
 Richmond Hotels
 Ringhoteis
 Roomzzz Aparthotel
 Route Inn
 Royal Orchid Central
 Royal Orchid Resorts & Heritage Hotels
 Royal Tulip Hotels
 SANA
 Sandman
 Sarovar Premiere
 Scholars Hotels
 Seasons Apartment
 Hotels
 Silver Cloud
 Soi Y Mar
 Somerset Hotels
 Sonesta ES Suites
 Starlight
 StayAt Hotel Apartments
 Sunroute
 Sweden Hotels
 Swiss-Belhotel
 Tanoa Hotel Group
 the b
 The Chifley
 The Fern Hotels & Resorts
 Timhotel Hotels
 TownePlace Suites
 Tryp by Wyndham
 Tulip Inn Hotel
 UNAWAY Hotels
 Unizo
 Valentin Hotels
 Van der Valk Hotels
 Vibe hotels
 Vila Gale
 Villa Fontaine
 Village Urban Resorts
 Washington Hotel
 Welcome Hotels

Westmark
 Wyndham Garden Hotel
 Xanterra Parks & Resorts
 Zenit Hoteles

Midscale
 A Victory Hotels
 Abad Hotels & Resorts
 ACHAT Hotels
 acom Hotel
 all seasonsHotels
 America's Best Suites
 AmericInn
 Anemon Hotels
 Aristos Hotels
 Aston International
 Azur Hotels & Resorts
 Barcelo Comfort
 Baymont Inn & Suites
 Best Western
 BlueBay Resorts
 Bonsai Hotels
 BreakFree Resort
 Cabot Lodge
 Campanile Hotel
 Canadas Best Value Inn
 Candlewood Suites
 Carris Hoteles
 Casa Andina Classic
 Catalonia
 Centro Hotels by Rotana
 Chisun Hotel
 Chisun Inn
 Citin Hotels
 Citrus Hotels
 Citrus Hotels & Resorts
 City Suites
 ClubHouse
 Cosmopolitan Hotels
 Country Garden Phoenix
 Hotel
 Crossings by GrandStay

Crystal Inn
 Dafam Hotels
 Dawa Roynet Hotels
 Dedeman Hotels
 Delfin Hotels
 Discovery Holiday Park
 Dormy Inn
 Eastin Easy
 ehotel
 Europa
 Eurotel Hotels
 Excemon
 FairBridge Inn
 Fern Residence
 Fiesta Hotels
 Fiesta Inn
 Fletcher Hotels
 FlexStay Inn
 Fortune Inn
 Fortune Park
 Fresh Hotels
 Good Inn Hotel
 GrandStay Residential
 Suites
 Grupotel
 Hawthorn Suites by
 Wyndham
 HNA Grand Hotel
 Homotel
 Hotel 81
 Hotel Gromada
 Hotel ibis
 Hotel RH
 Hotel Stars
 Hotel Wing International
 Hoteles H2
 Hoteles Vista
 ibis styles
 ibisHouse
 InnSuites Hotels
 JI Hotels
 JR Kyushu Hotel Group
 Keio Presso Inn

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Table 8. STR Chain Scales (World Hotel Grid Scale). Continued of the Midscale scale and continuation of the Economy scale.

STR Chain Scales – Global

Midscale continued

Keys Hotels & Resorts
Kibbutz Hotels
Kingsgate Hotels
Kyriad
La Quinta Inns & Suites
Lakeview Distinctive
Hotels
Leisure Inn
Lemon Tree Hotel
Libertel
Loyalty Inn
Maeva
Magnolia Hotels
MainStay Suites
Maple Hotels
Merit Hotels
Merlin
Metropolo JinJiang Hotels
Neo Hotels
Nishitetsu Inn
Novum Group
Oak Tree Inn
Oakwood Apartments
P'tit Dej Hotel
Palace Inn
Parkland Hotels & Resorts
Piao Home Inn
Prayag Hotels & Resorts
Premier Inn ME&A
Quality Inn
R&B Hotel
Ramada
Real de Minas
Red Lion Inn & Suites
Resol Hotel & Resort
Roc Hotels
Rode Inn Motels
Room-B Serviced
Apartment
Royal Orchid Suites
Sahid Hotels
Sarovar Portico

Scenic Hotel Suites &
Resorts
Sea Hotels
Sercotel Hotels
Settle Inn
Shilo Inn
Sidorme
Silka Hotels
Skytel
Sleep Inn
Smile Hotels
Soi
Sorat Hotels
Sorea Hotel
Sotetsu Fresa Inn
StayEasy by Southern Sun
Sun Maris Hotels
Super Hotel
Swallow Hotels
Swiss Inn
The Mosaic Collection
Tokyu Inn
Tokyu REI Hotels
Town Lodge
Travelodge, AUS
TREFF Hotels
TRH Hoteles
Vagabond Inn
Via Inn
Vienna Hotel
VIP Hotels
Vista
WelcomHeritage
Wingate by Wyndham
Yotel
Yotel QQ
3 Palms Hotels & Resorts

Economy

Affordable Suites of
America
Amaris Hotel by Santika
America's Best Inns
Americas Best Value Inn
Australis
B&B Hotels
Balladins
Best Hotels
Bestay Hotel Express
Budget Host
Budget Suites of America
Budgetel
City Comfort Inn
City Inn
City Junior
Commundo Tagungshotels
Country Hearth Inn
Crestwood Suites
Crossland Economy
Studios
Days Inn
Downtowner Inns
E-Z 8
easyHotel
Econo Lodge
Etap Hotel
Evergreen
Extended Stay America
Family Inns Of America
Fave Hotels
Fragrance Hotels
Garden Inns
Ginger Hotels
Goldmet Inn
Good Night Inns
Good Nite Inn
Grace Inn
Great Western
Greene King Inn
GreenTree Inns
GuestHouse Inns

Hanting
HNA Business Hotel
HNA Express Inn
Holiday Star Hotel
Home Inn
Home-Towne Suites
Hop Inn
Hotel AZ
Hotel Climat
Hotel F1
Hotel Formule 1
Hotel Livemax
Hotel Premiere Classe
Hoteles Serena
Howard Johnson
hub by Premier Inn
ibis budget
Inkeeper's Lodge
InTown Suites
Jameson Inn
Jin's Inn
JinJiang Inns
Key West Inn
Knights Inn
Kris Hoteles
Lemon Hotel
Lite Hotel
Master Hosts Inns
Masters Inn
Meininger Hotels
Microtel Inn & Suites
by Wyndham
Mister Bed Hotels
Motel 168
Motel 268
Motel 6
Motel One
NanYuan Inn
National 9
Nevsky Hotels
Old English Inn
Omena Hotels

One Hotels
Passport Inns
Pear Tree Inn
Pod Inn
POP! Hotel
Premier Inn
Quantum Hotel Group
Red Carpet Inns
Red Fox Hotels
Red Planet Hotels
Red Roof Inn
Road Lodge
Rodd Hotels & Resorts
Rodeway Inn
Savannah Suites
Scottish Inns
Select Inn
Shindom Inn
Starway
Studio 6
Suburban Extended
Stay Hotels
Sun 1
Sun Suites Hotels
Sundowner
Super 8
Swiss-Belinn
Thriftlodge
Toyoko Inn
Travelodge
Travelodge, UK
Tune Hotels
Value Place
Wei Bo Inns & Hotel
WoodSpring Suites
Zest Hotels
Zhongan Inn
Zleep Hotels
7 Days Inn

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Finally, another important bibliographical reference is the master's dissertation of Johanna Lira de Barros Carvalho, from the University Anhembi-Morumbi, entitled "Services and hospitality. Charm itineraries: a model for independent hosting media "(CARVALHO, 2015). Although her work is focused on the existing model of a company called Scriptwriting, the author has clearly and comprehensively synthesized existing models and authors on the subject. Since there is no standard global classification and countries have several classification systems in hosting media, the author systematized this in tables as follows:

Quadro 1 . Sistema de classificação. Castelli e Aldrigui

Classificação privada (CASTELLI, 2001) ou Classificação Comercial (ALDRIGUI,2007).	A empresa estabelece critérios de classificação e os estabelecimentos procuram enquadrar-se. Exemplo: Guias turísticos como o Michelin e o Guia Quatro Rodas.
Autoclassificação (CASTELLI, 2001) ou Classificação Independente (ALDRIGUI, 2007).	Muito parecida com a privada ou comercial, porém restringe-se a determinadas empresas. Muitos meios de hospedagem se autoclassificam como “o melhor” ou o “seis estrelas.” Não esclarecendo ao consumidor formas de comparação com outros estabelecimentos hoteleiros. Exemplo: Os grupos ou redes hoteleiras e associações de hotéis que possuem como membros empreendimentos com diferentes características identificadas por marcas ou serviços e qualidade nos produtos que possibilita orientar o consumidor.
Classificação oficial (ALDRIGUI,2007; CASTELLI, 2001)	Classificação implantada pelos governantes dos países. Exemplo: Sistemas voluntário ou obrigatórios de classificação hoteleira criados por autoridades nacionais ou internacionais.

Quadro 7 - Sistemas de classificação.

Fonte: Castelli (2001) e Aldrigui (2007). Adaptado pela autora (2014).

According to her, other authors, such as Vallen and Vallen (2005 apud (CARVALHO, 2015), are based on four more detailed and considered traditional classifications:

Table 2. Vallen and Vallen classification

Porte ou tamanho	Apesar de terem várias formas de padronização para medir o porte de um hotel, como o número de andares, área do terreno, número de funcionários etc. O mais tradicional é pelo número de unidades habitacionais (Uhs). O Porte é considerado a forma mais objetiva de classificação embora ainda seja incerta, pois os hotéis muitas vezes anunciam uma quantidade maior de apartamentos do que de fato existe destinados a hospedagem.
Classe ou categoria	Medidas subjetivas estão sendo disponibilizadas para classificação por categoria ou classe, porém ainda estão longe da perfeição. Dois métodos são utilizados para dividir e identificar os hotéis que seriam um procedimento que utiliza a diária média e outro o sistema de classificação mundial. O preço é o melhor critério de classificação quanto mais conforto e serviço mais dinheiro é despendido. Exemplos para identificação: Hotel de luxo; primeira classe; intermediários; econômico. Todos têm uma média de preços que se identificam com a denominação. Importante entender que os valores e classificações variam dependendo da região que estão situados, por exemplo, locais turísticos ou grandes centros urbanos não irão aplicar diárias similares a pequenas cidades de interior. Os sistemas de classificações formais ou informais, públicos ou privados são outro meio de identificar a categoria e cada país determina os seus sistemas e símbolos.
Tipo	A tipologia dos meios de hospedagem é outra forma de classificação que vem se transformando e mesmo que o conceito básico de abrigar ou alojar permaneça, muitas mudanças e diferentes tipos de hospedagem surgiram e continuam a surgir.
Plano ou sistema	O plano ou sistema operacional de um hotel é um meio objetivo de classificação. Os preços serão mais altos se o sistema inclui as refeições. Alguns hotéis possuem o sistema que inclui o café da manhã, outros a meia pensão (duas refeições) ou pensão completa (três refeições). No Brasil geralmente aplica -se o sistema incluindo o café da manhã na diária.

Quadro 8 - Classificações tradicionais em meios de hospedagem.

Fonte: Vallen e Vallen (2005). Adaptado pela autora (2014).

In her paper Carvalho (2015) also emphasizes that there is a very wide range of typologies used by the lodging media, both in Brazil and in other countries. According to the author, Beni (2002 apud Carvalho, 2015), points out that some typologies have the same denomination, but with very different proposals, for

example, Motel, which Brazil has sexual appeal, unlike the US which is the road hotels. Another example given by the author, are the inns that have historical reference in Portugal and Brazil are not necessarily historic establishments.

The hotels and the means of lodging interact with each other and will always be the object of much discussion, analysis and permanent adjustments regarding use, types, segments and classifications, whether in the academic world or in the private sector. Most of the innovations and developments in this area have proven that the emergence of new means of hosting, design and product come from the entrepreneurial market through its qualified investors, pension funds, independent owners, networks and hotel operators, as well as managers, consultants and developers of hotel assets that exist today worldwide. The adjectives and nouns currently used by the market to try to classify or segment types of hotels / lodging are widely used but not systematically by the incoming market, such as: Boutique Hotel, Ice Hotel, Long- stay), Apart-Hotel, Residence Hotel for the Elderly, among others. These are types of hotels that are being created and launched right now by independent entrepreneurs, hotel chains and investors.

What we can not disregard is that these types, segments and classifications arise due to the need of the market in full technological evolution, of the existing and demanded architecture and, above all, of the requirements of consumers for something more personalized and directed to the paying public. To add a little more context to the final considerations of this study, the reference to the authors' book Rules, Penner and Adams (2001), "Hotel design, planning, and development", is fundamental, as it presents works carried out in several years in the area architecture, development and planning for hotels as well as in the interior design area. The authors clearly show, according to their experiences with more than 50 types of hotels and lodging facilities, in addition to the other interrelated types, as shown in figure 3. According to them, the possibilities explored today and the future possibilities for hotels and accommodation can be segmented and classified through a market segmentation for both hotels small, medium or large, whether independent or chain hotels.

Figure 3. Types of hotels and hosting facilities currently available

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

When it comes to classification and segmentation of hotel typology is not an easy job to be organized, since different types of hotels arise according to the need of market innovation (customers) and the need of hotel chains to be able to offer new models, types and segments of hotel products to insert them into its business portfolio and increase its market share, attract new investments and improve its bottom line (profitability). These innovations also go through independent and small and medium-sized hotels in the state of São Paulo and Brazil. The independent hotels, many of them without segmentation and classification, represent about 80% of the total number of hotels existing in Brazil today. This amount demonstrates that there is an extensive field for the development, adequacy and distribution of information pertinent to this segment.

The bibliographic and documentary review served as a basis for understanding the current situation in terms of quantitative data, but a further study is needed, both in terms of quantitative and qualitative data regarding the state of the art of small and medium-sized housing to be possible to insert them in the context of the innovation and existing hotel practices. Offering data, distribution tools in the most varied sales channels available today, as well as the demand for information relevant to your local and regional market will enable you to access all kinds of up-to-date information about your niche market and strategic positioning to increase your Market Share.

The classifications proposed by the government agencies, as analyzed here, are focused more on the physical appropriateness of the hotels, an important item, however insufficient, since other aspects are also fundamental for classification / segmentation models: architectural aspects in relation to aesthetics, functionality, finish and items of furniture, furniture and equipment used; managerial aspects in financial and non-financial terms; aspects of the quality perceived by the client, and their positioning in relation to the average daily rate practiced; and aspects related to the leisure and business market.

The regionalization of tourism presented by the Ministry of Tourism of 2015 has objectively demonstrated, after several years of research, the need for a more up-to-date parameter that is in keeping with the current reality of tourist destinations in the country. This work emphasized the similar and complementary characteristics, by historical, cultural, economic or geographical identity of the destinations, as well as the fact that they are bordering or distributed in an adjoining way. This work

should be a starting point for a future proposal, based on the study presented here, to elaborate a single classification / segmentation matrix for the hotel media.

Another point of departure, besides this work of regionalization of the Ministry of Tourism, necessary for the elaboration of a single matrix, is the work already done by other authors and sectors of the hotel industry. For example, the proposals of the bibliographical research presented in this paper, such as those of Vallei and Vallei (apud Carvalho, 2015), Castelli (2001), Smith Travel Research (STR); the Forum of Hotel Operators of Brazil (FOHB) and Jones Lang Lasalle (JLL).

Although there is data for the hotel sector in the country, its dispersion justified the focus of this research that sought the compilation of existing data, government and companies that provide data in the market and already manifest through certain segmentations. With these existing data and with some adaptations from the already elaborated studies, it is possible to create a managerial and segmented matrix for the small and medium means of lodging existing in the Brazilian market. To obtain adhesion to a new matrix by the hoteliers in general and the small and medium means of hosting, it will be fundamental the proposal of a more targeted research, qualitative and quantitative, that seeks the involvement of independent hotels. The research will need to show current data on the architectural requirements, types of segments practiced and results obtained by each typology, contemporary management methods practiced, case studies available, accessibility to the sales channels offered today, better understanding of the market segments practiced through the agencies off-line travel and carriers, as well as the available direct sales technologies to its final consumers. For this it is necessary that the information reaches the small and medium hoteliers, to offer, thus, knowledge and greater adhesion of the same ones.

In short, knowing the number of hotels in the state of São Paulo, classifying and segmenting them with management tools and a permanent flow of information, it is possible to offer knowledge with added value and transform the current scenario into real conditions of growth and updating for the small and medium-sized lodging facilities in the state of São Paulo.

The changes and innovations in the hotel sector are emerging from the market initiative. For this reason, we believe that the changes in terms of hotel segmentation, currently with a range of different typologies, need to create a managerial matrix for the means of lodging small and medium-sized to be developed from existing data from governmental and non-governmental companies. The elaboration of this matrix must presuppose the interlocution between the academy and the private sector, in order to create a greater reliability and adhesion of all those involved. With regard to hotel industry in Brazil, the market

has always shown a greater dynamism for the introduction of new products and services when compared to the academy, but the academic structure contributes with production of knowledge, research and logical structure through proven data and experimentation. Knowledge, allied to the market, institutions and opportunities, generates the need and fundamental innovations for the economic and social development for the small and medium means of lodging in the country

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